

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Acronyms and abbreviations

CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EcoAudit	Streamlined Life Cycle Assessment tool provided by Granta Design
GWP	Global Warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MS	Milestone
PC	Project Coordinator
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Table 1 List of acronyms and abbreviations

Glossary of key terms:

Business model	An organisation’s chosen system of decisions and activities that determines how it creates, delivers and captures value over time.
Circular economy	A circular economy entails decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resource, and designing waste and pollution out of the system. It aims to keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each service life ¹ . A circular economy should build economic and social capital and regenerate natural systems.
Composite materials	A composite material is composed of at least two materials, which combine to give properties superior to those of the individual constituents. They typically result in lighter, stronger, more durable solutions compared to traditional materials ² . Composites are hybrid materials, the composition of which is determined by their components. The most familiar man-made composites are a polymer matrix reinforced by fibres of glass, carbon or Kevlar.
Composting	Process of controlled biological decomposition of biodegradable materials under managed conditions that are predominantly aerobic and that allow the development of thermophilic temperatures as a result of biologically-produced heat ³
Disposal	Any operation which is not <i>recovery</i> (see below) – even where the operation has a secondary consequence or leads to the reclamation of substances or of energy. This includes disposal by incineration where the incineration plant does not meet the EUs R1 energy recovery status ⁴ .
Prevention	Measures taken before a substance, material or product has become waste, that reduce the quantity of waste, the adverse impacts of the generated waste on environment and human health, and the content of harmful substances in materials and products.
Recovery	Any operation, the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function in the plant or wider economy ⁶ . This includes incineration facilities where the plant meets the EU’s Recovery plant (R1) energy recovery status ⁴ .
Recycling	Any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations ⁶ .

¹ Adopted from [The Ellen MacArthur Foundation](#) and the UK’s [Waste Resources Action Programme](#)

² Taken from [Composites UK](#)

³ Taken from PAS100-2011, Specification for composted materials.

⁴ See [EU guidance](#) on R1 status

Remanufacturing	Returning a used product to at least its original performance with a warranty that is equivalent to or better than that of the newly-manufactured product ⁵ .
Repair	Return a faulty or broken product, component or material back to a usable state. A repair may use remanufactured or reconditioned parts ⁴ .
Reuse	Any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived ⁶ .
Systems thinking	A holistic approach to understanding how different parts of a system can influence one another and the relationship of the system to the parts over time ⁶
Waste	Any substance or object which the holder discards, or intends or is required to discard ⁷ .
Waste hierarchy	The priority order in waste prevention and management: <i>prevention, reuse, recycling, recover, disposal</i> ⁸

Table 2 Glossary

⁵ Taken from BS 8887-2:2009 Design for manufacture, assembly, disassembly and end-of-life processing. Terms and definitions

⁶ Taken from BS 8001:2017, framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations-Guide

⁷ Taken from the [EU Waste Framework Directive](#)

⁸ Taken from BS 8001:2017, framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations-Guide

2 Executive Summary

The deliverable brings an overview of the EcoBulk consortia knowledge on the current design considerations, materials choices, value chain, and end users of the selected baseline products/components. The work performed represents an essential starting point for establishing and evaluating future improvements with respect to the current state of the art. The baseline is focused on describing several aspects related to sustainability and circular economy:

- **Supply chain:** Description of the current supply chain as first step towards the assessment of the social aspects as well as a reference for the potential benefits that the project would bring with the solutions that will be developed;
- **Technical requirements:** dedicated per type of product/component. These are quantitative and qualitative functional requirements that the product or the materials have to fulfil in order to provide the expected value to the final users. These requirements are also defined as a list of regulations and standards that the producers have to comply with in order to get the product in the market;
- **Critical aspects to increase material/product circularity:** these aspects are what guided the selection of the products/components as baseline. Each of the selected baselines is affected by one or more critical aspects that are hindering the circularity of the materials or the remanufacturing. See section 6.1.1 for more information;
- **Environmental aspects:** in the context of this reports the environmental aspects considered are:
 - **Carbon footprint** or Global Warming potential: The CO₂-equivalent mass of greenhouse gases (kg CO₂e), in kg, produced and released into the atmosphere as a consequence of the production of 1 kg of the material. There are a variety of 'greenhouse gases' that contribute to global warming, including carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide. The 'potency' of these gases can vary significantly from a global warming perspective and therefore it is conventional to report these emissions in terms of an equivalent mass of carbon dioxide - kg CO₂e.
 - **Embodied energy** or Cumulative Energy Demand: Gross Energy required to make 1 kg of the material from its ores or feedstocks, it is expressed in MJ (considering the Upper Heating Value of the fuels and energy used for the production).

The potential environmental impacts are calculated using Granta's Eco Audit module which consists of a streamlined LCA based on the Product Risk data module⁹. The scope of the evaluation is to elaborate an initial reference value for the further development expected in the next WPs activities.

The information provided is therefore a mix of data collected from partners and assessment elaborated with the support of reference database and literature (see references and appendix at the end of the document). The full set of data for each baseline is reported in a dedicated template developed in the context of the task (see Section **Error! Reference source not found.**). The information in the templates represents the reference

⁹ <https://www.grantadesign.com/products/ecoaudit/>

starting point for the re-design of the products/components in the context of the project, where the functional requirements disclosed will guide the definition for any new re-design activities (WP3 and WP4). It is important to underline that any new solutions shall fulfil the functional requirements as well as demonstrate that cost, environmental, and social performances are not hindered by the adoption of the new materials, technology, or design strategy. Moreover, the new solutions would need to demonstrate that thanks to new design strategies, material development and improved data management among actors of the supply chain (WP5) the circularity of materials and products is potentially increased. A summary of the baseline products and the reference KPIs are reported in the following table.

Table 3: Baseline products summary

Sector	Application	Reference Product(s)	Life span [Years]	Weight [kg/unit]	Target cost [€/unit]	Embodied Energy [MJ]	Carbon Footprint [kgCO ₂ eq]
Automotive	Car interior	Fascia Central Console	5 - 7	0.22 – 0.26	5 - 7	24 - 26	1 - 2
		Safety belt brackets	10	0.15 – 0.20	2 - 4	6 - 8	0.5 – 0.7
		4WD control frame	10	0.09 – 0.1	2.70 - 3.00	11 - 12	0.6 – 0.65
		Centre Console Cowlings	5 - 10	0.1 - 1.82	40 - 60	16 - 17	0.65 – 0.75
Furniture	Home Furniture	Upholstered bed	10	80 - 100	1300 - 1800	1800 - 1900	80 - 90
		Bookcase	10	90 - 110	500 - 700	1300 - 1400	40 - 50
Building	Structural	OSB Structural Panel	100	30 - 35	16 - 18	300 - 400	12 - 14
		Plywood structural panel	100	80 - 90	60 - 70	1000 - 1010	30 - 40
	Outdoor (fencing, decking, etc...)	Solid Panel/Plank	10 - 15	2 - 3	4 - 6	20 - 30	0.95 – 1.05
		Post/Pillar	10 - 15	8 - 12	3 - 4	120 - 130	4 – 5
Various	Internal/soundproofing, thermal and structural insulation	Non-woven - Thermal and structural insulation(1m ²)	10 - 15	35 - 45	150 - 170	3400 – 3600	120 – 130
		Non-woven - Floor carpets (1m ²)	10 - 15	0.8 - 1	3 - 5	70 – 80	3 – 4

Please note that full details are reported in baseline cards in **Error! Reference source not found.** As well as providing the reference point for the next developments, the [exercise of the] baseline defines a procedure for analysing existing products and components which may be used for detailed baseline analysis in future developments. The baseline description refers to both specific products and families of products. The products can be actually produced by one of the OEMs currently involved in the project, but can also represent semi-finished components or materials categories that may have no direct connection with project’s partners. Taking these aspects into account, the KPI reported in the above table (and in the dedicated cards) are sometime reported as wide range of values. Social aspects that cannot be easily summarised are not reported in the table above but stored in the dedicated cards. Further improvements to the social and environmental aspects are expected in the *WP 7 Life Cycle Thinking*.

3 Scope of the report

This report aims at describing the outcomes of the task 2.1 “*Social, environmental and economic baseline for the value and supply chain*” of the EcoBulk project. The task was focused on the definition of the baseline products/components to be used as a reference for the subsequent developments in terms of design strategies and material development towards Circular Economy in the three sectors under study, namely Automotive, Furniture and Building. The consortium capabilities in supporting activities in the product value chain (Table 5 Partners' contribution to product development) and materials development (Table 6 Partners material development capabilities) is investigated and reported in the dedicated paragraphs. In addition, the relevant partners have also defined the baseline. A dedicated session on Design for Circular Economy, contribution from TU Delft, is also included in the report.

3.1 Material family introduction

The information in this paragraph is based on content available in “*CES EduPack software, Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2018 (www.grantadesign.com)*.” In this context, the composite materials are described as a subset of the family “hybrid” materials.

Hybrids are combinations of two or more materials, with the aim to benefit from the attractive properties of each material and minimize their drawbacks. As such, we can say little about their composition, which is determined by their components. But of those man-made hybrids used in engineering, the most familiar are composites in which a polymer matrix is reinforced by fibers of glass, carbon or Kevlar.

The unique factor in the structure of hybrids is the choice of how their components are arranged: how much of each will we use? What will be their shape, and how will they be connected? The properties of a composite depend hugely on these “design variables”, such as whether they contain fibers or particles.

3.1.1 General properties: At a glance

Figure 1 Hybrid materials properties against Material Universe

3.1.2 Typical properties

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites are light, stiff, strong, and can be tough. Although polymer-based hybrids cannot be used above 250 °C because the polymer softens, at room temperature their performance

can be outstanding. Crucially, many hybrids are lighter than metals of the same strength, so today's increasing emphasis on high performance and fuel efficiency are strong drivers for their use.

3.1.3 Typical failure mechanisms

Hybrids have many failure modes, some of which are complex; which one will operate depends on the hybrid's design, as well as the choice of component materials. In fiber-reinforced composites, the fibers span cracks in the brittle matrix, and then are broken or pulled out during fracture.

3.1.4 Processability - Typical processes used

- A. Thermoset-based polymer matrix (epoxy, polyester, vinylester and others).

Polymer-matrix composites are formed by combining fibers with a two-part liquid mixture of resin and hardener, that react together to form a solid polymer matrix. This can be done by molding, winding or "laying-in" methods, depending on the type of fibers used and the shape of the part.

- B. Thermoplastic-based polymer matrix (polyethylene, polypropylene, polyvinylchloride and others).

Polymer-matrix composites are formed by combining fibers with molten polymer at elevated temperature characteristic to each type of polymer and inside the processing equipment. This can be done by molding or extrusion methods, depending on the type of fibers used and the shape of the part.

In contrast with thermoset-based polymer matrices, which are not recyclable back to their original manufacturing process, thermoplastic-based composites are recyclable and can be re-processed again in their original manufacturing process.

Moreover, it is foreseen that thermoplastic-based composites with existing technology could potentially recycle and re-manufacture thermoset-based composite waste as reinforcements in the thermoplastic polymer matrix.

3.1.5 Typical uses

Thermoset-based fiber-reinforced composites are used mainly in aerospace, transport and sports applications, where weight is crucial combined with adequate strength properties. Due to its relatively low cost, glass fiber-reinforced plastic or "fiberglass" has wider uses as a building material, in pipes, storage tanks and electronic circuit boards.

Thermoplastic-based fiber-reinforced composites are used mainly in building materials, deckings, sidings, facades, fencing, outdoor furniture and small storages and shelters, replacing typically wooden materials with moisture-resistant, insect- and maintenance-free applications. Mostly these products are made using recycled and waste polymers, thus contributing to circular economies.

3.2 Market overview

Use of composites in different industries

% share of materials worldwide, 2014

Figure 2 Use of composite by industry¹⁰

Composites are light, stable, corrosion-resistant and low-maintenance: thanks to these properties, prospects are excellent for the composite market.

The **composites market** is projected to grow from USD 72.58 Billion in 2016 to USD 115.43 Billion by 2022, at a CAGR of 8.13% between 2017 and 2022. The manufacturers of composites are signing supply agreements with various end-use industries to secure their position in the composites market¹¹. This positive market outlook was reflected at this year's COMPOSITES EUROPE, which as Europe's leading trade fair in the largest market puts on display the entire manufacturing process from raw materials to semi-finished goods to finished components, with a total of 406 exhibitors from 28 countries and 8,342 visitors.

Automotive engineering, aerospace and construction have been the main drivers propelling fibre composites and their use is becoming crucial in many industry

sectors ranging from the wind energy to the transportation, construction and infrastructure industries. The benefits of fiber composites are most impactful in multi-material lightweight construction. That's because it is now clear that the demands of modern lightweight construction can no longer be met by a single material; finding the best solutions instead requires hybrid lightweight construction¹².

As the use of composites grows, the question of how to dispose of **end-of-life composite parts** is also growing in importance. Traditional disposal routes such as landfill and incineration are becoming increasingly

¹⁰ <https://www.ft.com/content/0b386a0a-9c50-11e6-a6e4-8b8e77dd083a><http://www.lucintel.com/>

¹¹ Composites Market by Fiber Type (Glass, Carbon), Resin Type (Thermoset, Thermoplastic), Manufacturing Process (Layup, Filament Winding, Pultrusion), Application (Transportation, Aerospace & Defense, Wind Energy), Region - Global Forecast to 2022, marketsandmarkets.com, 2017

¹² Final Report on Composites Europe 2017, <http://www.compositimagazine.it/final-report-on-composites-europe-2017/>

restricted, and composites companies are looking for more sustainable solutions. The European Composites Industry Association (EuCIA) addressed this issue at its Information Day – Competitive Composites: Sustainability and Recycling Challenges – held at the European Parliament in Brussels in 2011

Composites material recycling, particularly reclamation of carbon fibers has been driven by at least three marketplace realities¹³ :

- The European Union’s end-of-life-vehicle (ELV) directive requiring that 85%, by weight, of the materials used in a car or light truck must be reusable or recyclable.
- The high manufacturing cost and high performance of carbon fibers making it an attractive recycling target, which is creating market for recycled fiber products, most notably from the automotive sector.
- Finally, the newest generations of consumers with environmental awareness, actively supporting recycling activities and closed-loop manufacturing, and seeking out goods with recycled content.

¹³ <https://www.compositesworld.com/blog/post/composites-recycling-is-gaining-traction>

4 Design for a Circular Economy

4.1 Design introduction

For composite products in a Circular Economy, design, materials selection, and end-of-life (EoL) scenarios are strongly interconnected. Here we will outline the design baseline for the EcoBulk product lines. This implies that a qualitative description of the initial state of design activities and goals within the project will be presented. This chapter starts with an introduction of the main aspects, material recycling and value recovery. Next, these aspects are used to describe the baseline of design considerations in EcoBulk.

4.1.1 Main aspects

The terms used related to materials and end-of-life processes are ambiguous. We will therefore first provide definitions for the terms as used here.

Composite: A description of composite materials is provided in chapter 4. The term “composite” encompasses a wide range of materials. At the general assembly in M6, the consortium has chosen to adopt the definition of a composite being a material composed of a matrix and a particle. This can range from small particles randomly distributed in a polymer matrix to a network of fibers embedded in a matrix.

Design of composite products is a complex task wherein many constraints interact¹⁴. Ability to tailor material composition and shape allows for highly integrated and optimised solutions. Much of the product lifecycle can be determined through design, directing the product towards certain usage or EoL scenarios.

End of Life of products (EoL) indicates the obsolescence of the product, i.e. the product is no longer used. This can be due to many reasons¹⁵, for example, Loss of function, or physical product break down. Also, although composites are physically durable, enabling a long product life, repair can be difficult due to their highly integrated nature. Other reasons for EoL include the loss of economic value or user desire. By addressing the causes, the EoL can be postponed and the product life extended. Recycling, repair, refurbishing and remanufacturing are well-known approaches to extend product life.

4.1.2 Recycling

When the need for the product and its components has ceased to exist, and extending product life is no longer an economically viable option, the next route is recycling of material. We distinguish three categories of recycling (Hopewell, Dvorak, & Kosior, 2009):

Primary recycling delivers a recycle quality equivalent to the original material; *secondary recycling* refers to a recycle with lower properties; *tertiary recycling* recovers the materials’ chemical constituents.

¹⁴ Perry, N., Bernard, A., Laroche, F., & Pompidou, S. (2012). Improving design for recycling – Application to composites. *CIRP Annals*, 61(1), 151–154.

¹⁵ Woodward, D. G. (1997). Life cycle costing—Theory, information acquisition and application. *International Journal of Project Management*, 15(6), 335–344.

Composites derive their specific quality from a combination of fiber & matrix. From this perspective, when the bond between fibre and matrix is broken, the resulting individual materials represent a lower quality than the original composite. Thus, for composites, primary recycling can be referred to as retaining fibre-matrix integrity and secondary recycling includes fibre-matrix separation. Technology is available for both approaches, but it is yet unclear which is most beneficial (Allwood, Ashby, Gutowski, & Worrell, 2011; Perry et al., 2012). Sometimes energy recovery is also referred to as *recycling*. However, this should be avoided because of the irreversible and complete loss of materials it incurs. *Material recycling* is defined as processing of waste for original or other purposes excluding energy recovery (European Parliament and Council, 2005; NEN-ISO, 2008).

A product part can be recovered in different sizes. For example, (Beauson, Bech, & Brøndsted, 2014) identified the following recycling solutions for wind turbine blades: entire blade, major blade parts, construction elements, shredding, and fibre/resin separation. The first approach leads to re-use of the still-functional part, the latter approaches can be considered as recycling, and result in loss of material quality, both structural and in size.

Figure 3 Recycling of wind turbine blades

4.1.3 Value

The value hill is a way to depict the product value over its lifetime (Achterberg, Hinfelaar, & Bocken, 2016). The visualisation does not accurately represent the specific route of a product, but does indicate the rise and fall of product value from initiation to end of life. During and after the use phase, product life extension strategies can be applied. A material could run through multiple successive recovery and use phases with minimal degradation per stage.

4.2 EcoBulk Design Baseline

4.2.1 EcoBulk consortium

The value hill can be used to position consortium members in the different stages of a product life cycle. Categorisation shows that most of the consortium members are involved with either the beginning of product life (materials & product manufacturing) or end of life (waste management and sorting). Use phase

and product recovery activities are not represented by the industry partners. This gap is in part filled by the knowledge and ongoing research by the partners from academia and research institutes.

Figure 4 Value hill with EcoBulk project partners

4.2.2 Product design

Closing the loop for products commonly concentrates on the recycling of materials at the end of the functional product life, usually resulting in a lower quality material as well as loss of material. This is true for most materials, but especially for composites. Due to their often specific applications, these materials are tailored to specific use, and exhibit a complex composition and structure. A shredding process leaves a highly undefined material mixture, with widely varying composition. However, closing the loop is as much about the first use cycle as succeeding use cycles. This implies that, in addition to recycling, attention should also be given to maintenance, repair, refurbishment, and remanufacturing. To evaluate the state of circular product design at the start of the EcoBulk project, data was collected from the manufacturing partners to evaluate the following design considerations:

1. To what extent is EoL recovery (implying repair, remanufacturing and recycling) considered in the design stage?
2. To what extent are recycled materials used for product manufacturing?

Their responses have been sorted by industry sector: automotive (MAIER, CRF/Fiat, Microcab), construction components (Conenor), and furniture (Moretti Compact).

4.2.2.1 Automotive

In general, automotive industry is subject to the directive on end-of life vehicles (ELVs) (Directive 2000/53/EC - the "ELV Directive") requiring a recycling rate of 85% weight (European Parliament and Council, 2005). Plastic parts exceeding 100 g and elastomeric parts exceeding 200 g have to be marked with their material identification (European Parliament and Council, 2003) using the ISO identification system. An example, polypropylene filled with 10% mineral powder is coded as >PP-MD10< and an epoxy-glass fibre composite with a 35% fibre content as >EP-GF25< (NEN-ISO, 2016).

During the initial design stage, recycling is taken into account by calculating the recyclability rate of the vehicle and its components. In ISO 22628, the recycling rate is based on how the components are disassembled, re-used, and recycled. In line with the standard, car manufacturers have developed their own design guidelines, for example the specification sheet shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Example of specification sheet used by Renault designers¹⁶

In practice, vehicle end of life involves a number of disassembly steps, recovering valuable components and materials. As Enrico Mangino from Centro Ricerche Fiat (CRF) explains "At the end of life of a car, all parts that can be re-used are disassembled, like doors, hood, trunk, etc. Big mono-material parts are removed

¹⁶ Froelich, D., Maris, E., Haoues, N., Chemineau, L., Renard, H., Abraham, F., & Lassartesses, R. (2007). State of the art of plastic sorting and recycling: Feedback to vehicle design. *Minerals Engineering*, 20(9 SPEC. ISS.), 902–912.

(bumpers, glass) and recycled separately. Finally what remains is compressed and shredded. After shredding, the remainder of materials is sorted.”

MAIER, a large supplier of components for the automotive industry, complies to the ELV regulation by marking parts larger than 100 g as well as smaller parts when shape allows. Material information is documented and attached to the product drawings for future reference. MAIER uses its proprietary design for recycling guidelines in product development and calculates the recycling rate of the product using a questionnaire, where the desired value is set by the client car maker.

Recycled materials are used, and taken into account, from the earliest phases of product design. Recycled plastics are sourced from post-industrial material scrap, not from EoL waste. From the various recovery options discussed in the introduction, only secondary recycling is applied.

Fiat facilitates recycling by marking all parts exceeding 50 g with the material type. **CRF** (the research division of Fiat) aims to improve the recyclability of parts through applying easier disassembly systems. Partially-recycled materials are used for ventilation ducts and wheel covers.

Application of recycled materials is hampered by their reduced mechanical properties and UV resistance. Materials recycled from industrial processes are preferred over materials recycled from EoL vehicles as the supply from industry is better defined in terms of source and quality. Materials recovered from EoL tend to suffer from degradation during their previous life. CRF investigates the use of recycled plastics in non-structural and non-visible applications such as ventilation ducts. From the various recovery options discussed in the introduction, only secondary recycling is applied.

Microcab's activities are smaller of scale and more focused on R&D than production. This allows more design freedom and demonstration of 'eco' thinking in small fleets of real, road-going vehicles. End-of-life recovery on both product and material level is considered in the design stage by using a modular approach. The chassis has an open platform design and a long life expectancy. All systems within the chassis are modular (battery pack, fuel cell, hydrogen system, motor system, etc.) and body parts can be removed easily. During the life of the vehicle, these systems and components can be upgraded or replaced, extending product life. The modular setup also allows for dismantling and sorting of parts by material type to accommodate recycling. From the various recovery options discussed in the introduction, part re-use and secondary recycling is applied.

Although open to the suggestion, recycled materials have not been used. Parts are sourced from other suppliers and Microcab (generally) does not control their material stream. Use of compressed waste plastics has been investigated but not implemented due to the high tooling costs.

4.2.2.2 Building

Conenor follows a strongly recycled and waste material focused approach up to 95% in weight, not directly involving product design considerations. Conenor uses its proprietary Conex extrusion technique to make intermediate materials for project partners. For example, extruded panels, beams and boards to use in

building and construction applications. The extruded material can be returned shredded and re-used for new extrusion profiles at the end of life.

Conenor aims to use waste materials that currently have little or no recycling solutions. Recycled materials used include polymers PP, PE, ABS, from consumer and building market products, wood (construction & demolition, furniture) and thermoset composites (wind turbine blade and manufacturing dust) waste.

4.2.2.3 Furniture

The main material of **Moretti Compact** furniture is chipboard. The furniture is considered 75% recyclable due to the materials used. This is not due to specific design choices. End of life of the products is currently unknown and not taken into account in design. The used chipboard is declared to be made of 100% recycled wood.

In the course of the EcoBulk project, Moretti aims to improve the recyclability of materials by allowing easier disassembly of the product and separation of the materials. For example, separating ABS edge strips from particleboard panels. Also, Moretti aims to develop a formaldehyde-free particle board, if possible with a lower density.

Design considerations described by the companies are summarized in Table 4, sorted by type of recovery or recycling level. The table shows that on the level of individual parts, no recovery solutions are applied in which parts maintain their original function. Materials are recycled at a secondary level, downgrading the material.

company	Parts recovery			Material recycling		
	repair	refurbish	re-use	primary	secondary	tertiary
MAIER					plastic marking	
CRF, Fiat					plastic marking	
Microcab					modular design materials selection	
Conenor					materials selection	
Moretti compact						

Table 4 Summary of design considerations taking product EoL into account

4.3 Summary

The scope of EcoBulk is composite materials. So, when a composite is used for a part of a complete product, the composite part is evaluated.

- The value hill categorisation and company responses indicate that the EcoBulk consortium composition is skewed towards material recycling rather than product recovery.
- When using recycled plastic, post -industrial scrap is preferred to EoL material because of the higher certainty of quality and origin.
- When product EoL is taken into account in the design, materials recycling is aimed at secondary recycling methods.
- For the individual composite parts, no higher-level recovery strategies are used.

- All manufacturing companies choose to use recycled materials in their products.
- Current product design provides little drive for product and material recovery; the most powerful influence for the EoL scenario comes from material selection.

5 Industrial sectors overview

5.1 State of the art and future challenges in the automotive sector

The automotive industry is highly dependent on raw materials and some precious and rare earth metals , which represents a major obstacle and presents significant supply challenges.

*With 60% of the global supply going into car manufacturing, the automotive industry is the top consumer of lead in the world and according to some studies, these reserves will run out in 2030. Besides the shortages and supply challenges of the metals, rare or not, the rise in global demand for raw materials has created extraordinary price increases. For the automotive industry, these added costs are going up by several million euros year on year.*¹⁷

Being able to anticipate any shortages, and securing supply are the primary concerns for the manufacturers, and technological solutions are being developed to limit current dependence on earth metals. Equally, the geopolitical issues around raw materials are being integrated at EU level, and one of the policies in discussion is recycling. Twelve million vehicles are taken off the roads every year in the European Union, which amounts to millions of tonnes of what constitutes a valuable resource. The utilisation of this secondary resource, investing in recycling technologies, and increasing the use of recycled material has been found to provide a promising outlook¹⁸.

Besides this, new designs in the automotive sector need to take into account end-of-life issues. The Directive 2000/53/EC ([Directive 2000/53/EC - the "ELV Directive"](#)) on end-of life vehicles (ELVs) aims at making dismantling and recycling of ELVs more environmentally friendly and sets clear quantified targets for reuse, recycling and recovery of the ELVs and their components. It also pushes producers to manufacture new vehicles without hazardous substances (in particular lead, mercury, cadmium and hexavalent chromium), thus promoting the reuse, recyclability and recovery of waste vehicles ([Directive 2005/64/EC](#) on the type-approval of motor-vehicles with regards to their reusability, recyclability and recoverability)¹⁹.

The recycling options for ELV are dependent on the materials used for vehicle manufacturing and the assembly methods.

¹⁷ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy/interactive-diagram/the-circular-economy-applied-to-the-automotive-industry>

¹⁸ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy/interactive-diagram/the-circular-economy-applied-to-the-automotive-industry>

¹⁹ End-of-Life Vehicle Recycling in the European Union, N. Kanari, J.-L. Pineau, and S. Shallari, JOM 2003

Vehicle composition, in particular, is shifting toward light materials such as aluminium and polymeric constituents which can result in improved fuel economy and reduced emissions. It is believed that a 100 kg weight reduction of a vehicle results in a fuel savings in a range between 0.25 and 0.35l per 100km for gasoline cars and 0.2 and 0.25l per 100km for diesel cars²⁰.

Taking into account that the average lifespan of a car in use is 10-15 years, ELVs in the recycling chain today were manufactured in the 2000-2010s. The average composition of an EU car in 2008 is illustrated in Figure 6 which shows the increase of aluminium content (~8%) in the total car weight²¹. Ferrous and non-ferrous metals (Zn, Cu, Mg, and Pb) constitute about 67.5% of the vehicle while plastics are about ~9.3%.

Figure 6 Material composition for a diesel car (JRC 2008)

Plastics and composites use is increasing in car manufacturing, but their recycling is complex and challenging because of their heterogeneous nature and their strong connections to other plastics, resulting in difficulties in the separation for recycling²². Thermoset materials present a further challenge since they cannot be melted down and recycled due to their permanent cross-link structure. Even when a material can be recycled, it is often still landfilled because it cannot actually be physically recovered. The following picture gives an overview of the disposal route for ELV

²⁰http://www.world-aluminium.org/media/filer_public/2018/01/02/ifeu_-_energy_savings_by_light-weighting_2016_update_final_3-2017_corrected_12-2017.pdf

²¹ "Plastics: A Material of Choice for the Automotive Industry" (Brussels, Belgium: Association of Plastics Manufacturers in Europe, 1999), www.apme.org (April 2003).

²² Buekens, A.; Zhou, X. Recycling plastics from automotive shredder residues: A review. *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manag.* 2014, 16, 398–414

Figure 7 The disposal route for end-of-life vehicles²³

5.2 State of the art and future challenges in the furniture sector

Around a quarter of the world’s furniture is manufactured within the European Union, representing a €84 billion market that equates to an EU28 consumption of ~10.5 million tonnes of furniture per annum while employing approximately 1 million European workers and consisting of, predominantly, SMEs²⁴.

Figure 8 Furniture material breakdown

Ten million tonnes of furniture is discarded by businesses and consumers in EU Member States each year, the majority of which is destined for either landfill or incineration.

²³ <http://www.tms.org/pubs/journals/JOM/0308/Kanari-0308.html>

²⁴ <http://circulatenews.org/2015/11/developing-a-circular-economy-approach-in-the-furniture-sector/>

According to the *Circular Economy Opportunities in the Furniture Sector* report from European Environmental Bureau (EEB) (2017), the main barriers to a circular furniture sector are:

- Lower quality materials and poor design
- REACH Regulation (on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals)
- Poor consumer information and availability of spares
- Limited collection and reverse logistics infrastructure
- High cost of repair and refurbishment
- Weak demand for second-hand furniture
- Poor demand for recycled materials
- Weak over-arching policy drivers.

According to European Federation of Furniture Manufacturers (UEA) statistics, furniture waste in the EU accounts for more than 4% of the total municipal solid waste (MSW) stream. Comparably, other data sources at Member State level estimate furniture waste from domestic sources accounting for between 2% and 5% of MSW. Based on this data, it is estimated that household furniture represents between 2% and 5% of MSW in the EU28. Assuming waste generation reflects a similar pattern to consumption, waste arising from commercial sources has been assumed to contribute 18% of total furniture waste generation across the sector. Assuming an average composition of 3.75% furniture in MSW, the total annual EU28 furniture waste equates to 10.78 million tonnes, reflecting a yearly substitution of new versus discarded furniture. There is limited information on end of life treatment of furniture. According to European Federation of Furniture Manufacturers (UEA) statistics, 80% to 90% of the EU furniture waste in MSW is incinerated or sent to landfill, with ~10% recycled²⁵.

Whilst recycling rates in the EU have improved through the introduction of policies such as the Landfill Directive, there is minimal activity in higher-value circular resource flows, with remanufacturing accounting for less than 2% of the EU manufacturing turnover. Reuse of furniture is common, but this tends to be on a small scale and with local social goals in mind rather than larger scale environmental and economic ones.

5.3 State of the art and future challenges in the building sector

The biggest volume of waste in Europe is produced by construction and demolition work. According to information given by the European Statistical Office EUROSTAT, 48% of the waste produced comes from construction and demolition work and further 15 % of the waste produced comes from mining and stone and earth extraction in the 15 EU states²⁶. To avoid waste, the European Union laid down binding recycling quota for the member states of the European Union in the amended EU Waste Framework Directive which came into force in 2010. The recycling quota for construction and demolition waste is on average to be increased to 70% of the waste produced until 2020. It is the aim to produce high-quality construction products of construction waste in the sense of a closed cycle. By a minimum recycling quota of 70%, the environment

²⁵ Report-on-the-Circular-Economy-in-the-Furniture-Sector from European Environmental Bureau (EEB) (2017)

²⁶ http://www.eqar.info/fileadmin/eqar/paper/RC_environmental-resources_protection.pdf

will be protected in multiple respects. High-quality recycled building materials are an equally good substitute for natural building materials, thus contributing to a protection of landscape by reducing extraction areas and pits respectively. By recycling building materials on site or in the nearer region, significant quantities of CO₂ are saved which otherwise would be released by removing waste and supplying natural building materials frequently over large distances. Thus, recycling of building materials may also pay a remarkable contribution to climate protection. So far recycled building materials have been used in the construction of roads, road foundations, and sports grounds, for noise protection walls, earth banks and in landscape construction. They are also increasingly used as aggregates in the concrete and stone production²⁷.

Through recovery, recycling and/or re-use strategies, the construction industry can make a valuable contribution to the circular economy. However, there are a number of challenges that the construction industry must overcome in order to fully adopt circular economy principles²⁸:

- At present, the raw materials used within the sector are generally abundant and relatively low in value. A component's value affects how it is dealt with at the end-of-life stage and the distance it can viably be transported to a site of re-use or remanufacture.
- While 'design for re-use in manufacture' is possible at building (product) level as, for example, at the end of one building's life intact clay roof tiles may be removed and re-used on another building, for re-use in manufacture, it is essential that material contamination is prevented. In the case of direct re-use at the building level, it requires careful removal, transport and replacement of the components to avoid damage and maintain functionality.
- 'Design for material recovery' requires collaboration along the full supply chain of product designers, users, policy makers and component manufacturers to ensure that raw materials can be used and reused many times over. In the construction industry, this principle IS being adopted in building management through the use of *Building Information Modeling* (BIM), which will play an essential role in both maintenance and extending the useful life of a building. However, there is considerable effort required to ensure that there is a viable market for recovered components and recycled raw materials within the construction industry.

In both new construction projects and renovation work, design professionals are continuing to discover the advantages of green building solutions: plastic composite building products, including durability, light weight, corrosion resistance, high strength, and low maintenance requirements. These plastic materials obtain much of their versatility because they can be engineered to provide specific performance characteristics. Technically known as fiber-reinforced plastics or fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP), plastic composites generally comprise two components: a reinforcement fiber and a polymer binder (often called a matrix). The

²⁷ Recycling of building materials European market of quality-assured recycled building materials, EQAR – European Quality Association for Recycling e.V.

²⁸ <https://wienerberger.co.uk/about-us/role-of-construction-materials-in-the-circular-economy>

unique blend of properties designed into the final product allows designers and manufacturers to substitute high-performance plastic composites for traditional materials. Examples are²⁹:

- Cast plastic polymers, which encompass cultured marble, cultured granite, cultured onyx, and solid-surface products, are chemically bonded and mineral-filled materials used in a wide range of household and commercial applications (e.g. countertops, vanities, shower receptors, bathtubs, enclosure sets, fireplace surrounds, windowsills, wall panels, floor tiles, whirlpool baths, and molding accents).
- Structural insulated panels (SIPs) featuring a core of expanded polystyrene (or in some instances, extruded polystyrene [XPS] or polyisocyanurate [polyiso]) insulation sandwiched between two thin slices of OSB resulting in floor/wall/roof panel strong, lightweight, and that can be designed to have exceptional insulation properties.
- Wood-plastic composites (WPC) used to replace exterior decking and moldings, doorjambs, fencing, and other applications where durability is an important performance attribute. Co-extruded wood composite used for railings, comprising a core of polyvinyl chloride (PVC) or ABS resin and wood fiber capped by a weatherable polyvinyl chloride (PVC) or acrylonitrile-styrene-acrylate (ASA) protective layer.

6 Baseline definition – a methodological approach

The first steps for the baseline definition were based on the definition of the value chain of the baseline products, as described in Figure 9 below, and the related role of each partner in the consortium to any of the value chain phases. The main phases analysed can be summarized in:

- **Material development and production:** in this phase, the focus is on what materials are used for the products or components, which are the criteria for the selection of those materials (functional requirements) and what production processes are normally used, e.g. polymer moulding, sheet rolling etc. This information is collected for each baseline to support the environmental assessment from a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) point of view
- **Product Design:** a dedicated session on the design criteria has been carried out by TU Delft, and reported in section 4. These criteria are investigated to take into account the value of circularity aspects for the designer as well the role of the final users in relation to the products.
- **Product Manufacture:** in this phase, the assembly, the required standard, and legislation have been analysed from the point of view of the manufacturer. It also takes into account the production volume, since a more sustainable, circular solution will cope with the real requirements that manufacturers have to deal with.
- **Post use and collection:** these have been analysed at industrial sector scale, and reported in the previous chapters. The end of life of products and materials is heavily affected by the market and

²⁹ <https://greenbuildingsolutions.org/blog/composites-high-performance-building-solutions/>

geographical conditions in which the product is disposed. More in-depth analysis on the actual end-of-life scenario of the baseline product would be carried out in the following projects tasks.

Figure 9 EcoBulk reference value chain

Table 5 below describes the roles of partners in the project and their contribution to the different stages of product development expected in the EcoBulk project. The main actors defining the baseline products were the partners actually involved in the product production in the three sectors investigated and the materials manufacturers (e.g. NTT and Conenor). Some of the partners in the consortium are not mentioned since their role will be more focused in the general project activities such as project management, communication and exploitation.

	Automotive	Furniture	Buildings
Product design	CRF; ITENE; MAIER; MICROCAB; TU Delft; Technoplants;	CONENOR; FCBA; ITENE; KEAS; MORETTI; TU Delft; Technoplants;	CONENOR; FCBA; ITENE; TU Delft; Technoplants;
Joints, connections and fasteners	AKZO; CRF; MAIER; MICROCAB; LIPOR; TU Delft;	AKZO; CONENOR; TU Delft;	AKZO; CONENOR; LIPOR; TU Delft;
Composite development and production	AIMPLAS; AKZO; CRF; CNR; COVENTIVE; CRANFIELD UNI; NTT; Tecnar GmbH;	AIMPLAS; AKZO; CONENOR; CNR; CRANFIELD UNI; KEAS; NTT; Tecnar GmbH;	AIMPLAS; AKZO; CONENOR; CNR; CRANFIELD UNI; NTT; Tecnar GmbH;
Product manufacture	CRF; MAIER; MICROCAB;	CONENOR; KEAS; MORETTI;	CONENOR;
Piloting	CRF; CRANFIELD UNI; MAIER; MICROCAB; LIPOR; Technoplants;	CRANFIELD UNI; FCBA; MORETTI; Technoplants;	CRANFIELD UNI; FCBA; LIPOR; Technoplants;
Post use phase (end of life collection and treatment)	AIMPLAS; BELLVER; IRIS; ITENE; NTT; LIPOR; TOMRA; UPC;	AIMPLAS; FCBA; ITENE; NTT; UPC;	AIMPLAS; FCBA; ITENE; NTT; LIPOR; UPC;

Table 5 Partners' contribution to product development

6.1.1 Selection criteria

The criteria used for the selection of the baseline products in the Automotive, Furniture and Building sectors are all focused in defining the critical aspects that, currently, can be described as critical for the implementation of circular strategies. These criteria try to identify the main issues that may cause problem in the application of reuse/remanufacture products and components, as well as identify potential application for the composite, where composite inner properties can actually improve the quality/performance of the product.

- **Difficulties to Recover/Recycle:** some products are by design particularly difficult to be recycled or recovered for manufacturing. This may be due to a variety of factors, e.g. raw material price fluctuation that make difficult to estimate the value of recovering versus producing from virgin feedstock. Moreover, difficulties for the end-of-life recyclability may be caused by assembly solutions (e.g. adhesives) or the presence of chemicals that may cause problems in the recycling problem or make the product not compliant with the current or future legislation requirements;
- **Difficulties in adopting/accepting recycled materials:** for all products and components that currently do not utilize the recycled materials because of specific requirements, such as esthetical, that are difficult to fulfil because of poor or no control on the recycled material quality. These could be used as an opportunity to improve the collection/recycle processes as well as to control the uncertainty of the recycled material properties, or to develop design strategies in the natural uncertainty of the recycled materials;
- **Critical application where composite materials can be a credible alternative:** the criteria was selected to check if the product/material to baseline could represent a valid candidate for the material substitution. Composites are often optimal candidates for the lightweight design, but the recyclability of these materials may cause problems in the production and end-of-life stages. Other factors such as cost and assembly may represent critical aspects of the adoption of composites into product design.
- **Applicability/feasibility of circular economy strategies and new business models:** some product categories are better matched to a variety of strategies to implement circular economy solutions (e.g. recovery systems, product as a service, etc.). These may be low volume production products, products that shall be sold as service such as washing machines, or where end-of-life collection streams are already well structured, e.g. packaging.

6.1.2 KPIs for the baseline

The KPIs for the creation of the Baseline do reflect the value chain aspects mentioned above, and are detailed for each baseline product in the dedicated template reported in the following chapter. The description of the KPIs is reported hereinafter.

- **Supply chain:** description of the current supply chain as first step towards the assessment of the social aspects, as well as a reference for the potential benefits that the project would bring with the solutions that will be developed;

- **Technical requirements:** dedicated per type of product/component. These are quantitative and qualitative functional requirements that the product or the materials have to fulfil in order to provide the expected value to the final users. These requirements are also defined as a list of regulations and standards that the producers have to comply with in order to get the product in the market;
- **Critical aspects to increase material/product circularity:** these aspects are what guided the selection of the products/components as baseline. Each of the selected baselines is affected by one or more critical aspects that are hindering the circularity of the materials or the remanufacturing. See section 6.1.1 for more information;
- **Environmental aspects:** in the context of this report, the environmental aspects considered are:
 - **Carbon footprint** or Global Warming potential: The CO₂-equivalent mass of greenhouse gases (kg CO₂e), in kg, produced and released into the atmosphere as a consequence of the production of 1 kg of the material. There are a variety of 'greenhouse gases' that contribute to global warming, including carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide. The 'potency' of these gases can vary significantly from a global warming perspective and therefore it is conventional to report these emissions in terms of an equivalent mass of carbon dioxide - kg CO₂e.
 - **Embodied energy** or Cumulative Energy Demand: Gross Energy required to make 1 kg of the material from its ores or feedstocks, it is expressed in MJ (considering the Upper Heating Value of the fuels and energy used for the production)

The potential environmental impacts are calculated using Granta's Eco Audit module which consists in a streamlined LCA based on the Product Risks data module³⁰. The scope of the evaluation is to elaborate an initial reference value for the further development expected in the next WPs activities.

The information provided in the baseline cards are therefore a mix of data collected from partners and assessment elaborated with the support of reference database and literature (see references and appendix at the end of the document).

6.2 EcoBulk consortium: Capabilities in developing materials

In order to give a better idea of the capability of the consortium to implement new solutions in the project, an internal investigation of the partners was carried out. The results are reported in the following table. This assessment, coupled with the list of the potential new materials and solution available (see Table 7 List of potential substitution materials) made available by the consortium, helped in defining the baseline products and reducing the potential possible application that may have been choose.

³⁰ <http://www.grantadesign.com/products/mi/pi.htm>

Organization Short Name	Material development	Estimated Material Production Capacity [ton/yr]	Production of specimen for Testing [True/False]	Material Testing facilities [True/False]	Product testing facilities [True/False]
AKZO	TRUE (Resin)	Lab scale			
CRF					TRUE
CONENOR	TRUE	Pilot			
CNR			TRUE	TRUE	
COVENTIVE	TRUE	Pilot	TRUE	TRUE	FALSE
CRANFIELD UNI	TRUE				
FCBA				TRUE	TRUE
KEAS	TRUE	300,000	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
MAIER					TRUE
MICROCAB					TRUE
NTT	TRUE				
Technoplants	TRUE				
Tecnar GmbH	TRUE	10,000	TRUE	TRUE	FALSE

Table 6 Partners material development capabilities

Table 7 shows the list of materials that are made available within the consortium capabilities and that would be investigated as potential substitute for the baseline products selected.

Note: the list below is not exhaustive and could be subject to revision as the project progresses.

Partner	Material identification / name	Type	Feedstock	Main process route	Shape
CONENOR	Hollow bar 60x40x8 mm	Semi-finished	Recycled (various)	Extrusion Single & Multilayer	Hollow bar
	Solid Plank 120x30 mm				Solid Plank
	Hollow Board 140x28 mm				Hollow Board
	Solid Panel 390x5 mm				Solid Panel
	Solid Panel 390x10 mm				Solid Panel
	Solid Panel 390x15 mm				Solid Panel
	Tube/Pole 52x3,5 mm				Tube/Pole
	Tube/Pole 110x10 mm				Tube/Pole
	Plate 150x10 mm				Plate
	Column 125x125 mm				Column
COVENTIVE	Carbon fibre/PP - LFT (long fibre thermoplastic) pellets	Compound/Pellets	Recycled and waste fibres	Injection moulding	complex 3D

Partner	Material identification / name	Type	Feedstock	Main process route	Shape
	Carbon fibre/PA6 - LFT (long fibre thermoplastic) pellets				
NTT	wood chips -granules	Compound/Pellets	Recycled	Airlaid	Flat panel/3D composites
	discarded leather fibers / yarns / fabrics	Waste			
	plastic / foam wastes, in granules or cut-outs				
KEAS	Particle board (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished	Virgin and Partially Recycled Wood	Hot Pressing	Flat Board (8 mm to 38 mm thick, 2100X2800 mm, 1830X3660 mm, can be sized)
	Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished	Virgin Wood		
	Moisture Resistant MDF (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished			
	Moisture Resistant Particleboard (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished	Virgin and Partially Recycled Wood		
	Fire Retardant MDF (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished	Virgin Wood		
	Fire Retardant Particleboard (Raw/melamine faced)	Semi-finished	Virgin and Partially Recycled Wood		
	Laminate Flooring	Semi-finished	Virgin Wood	Hot Pressing, then, high density fibreboard (HDF) pressed by multi layers, including wear layer, balance layer, etc.	Panel, ready for flooring. (8 mm thick, 1295X193 mm, 1205X197 mm)
DOORLAM	Semi-finished	Virgin Wood	4 mm MDF coated with decorative paper	Door panel (4 mm thick, 183X2100 mm)	
Tecnaro GmbH	PLA	Compound/Pellets	Biobased	Extrusion/Injection moulding	Granule
	Bio-PE				
	Bio-PA				
	Lignin				
	Petrol-based PP		Mineral oil based matrix		

Table 7 List of potential substitution materials Base line products

6.2.1 Selected products

The selected baseline products focus on state-of-the-art materials and manufacturing processes which are commercialized by one of the consortium partners, or which represent the reference market of new material development, and for which data is available around the efficiency and cost structure of the materials and processes. To be able to predict the performance of the part for the different possible materials options versus the requirements, the selection of the products has been done considering the availability of information on the material/product through the manufacturing process (process), the performance for the produced part, the end-of-life scenario, including targeted re-use of “recycles” in applications with defined material value.

In the following tables, a summary of the selected product is reported as well as a more detailed description of the criteria used for the selection of any baseline and the reference end-of-life scenario per industry sector investigated.

Sector	Application	Material(s)	Reference Product(s)	Selection Criteria				Partner	
				Currently difficult to be Recovered Recycled	Difficult to accept Recycled Reused materials	Critical application	Circular economy potential application		
Automotive	Car interior	PC+ABS	Fascia Central Console	Y	Y	N	Y	MAIER	
		Metal	Safety belt brackets	Y	Y	Y	N	CR Fiat	
		ABS	Trim for central panel	Y	Y	N	N		
		ABS	Centre Console Cowlings	Y	N	N	Y	Microcab	
Furniture	Home Furniture	Various	Upholstered bed	N	Y	Y	Y	Moretti	
			Bookcase	N	Y	Y	Y		
Building	Structural	Softwood	OSB structural panel	N	Y	Y	Y	FSCB	
		Plywood	plywood structural panel	N	N	N	Y		
	Outdoor (fencing, decking, etc...)	Sawn timber	Panel		N	N	Y	Y	Conenor Exergy
			Pillars outdoor		N	N	Y	Y	
Various	Internal/soundproofing, thermal and structural insulation	PET, PP, Low Melt, or blends	Non-woven	Y	N	Y	Y	NTT Tecnoplants	

Table 8 Baseline products and selection criteria

Reference Product(s)	Selection Criteria			
	Currently difficult to be Recovered/Recycled	Difficult to accept Recycled Reused materials	Critical application	Circular economy potential application
Fascia Central Console	Currently downcycled, mixed plastics, plastics with coatings/paints	Aesthetic factors limiting use of recycled materials. Technical specifications regarding impact resistance, VOC, fogging, odour, colour, chemical resistance		Source of recycled materials for the production of thermoplastic compounds.
Safety belt brackets	Currently grinded with the whole vehicle (metals, polymers, ..)	High structural requirements	Safety component	
Trim for central panel	Currently grinded with the whole vehicle (metals, polymers, ..)	Aesthetic factors prevent the use of recycled polymers		
Centre Console Cowlings	3D printed part at prototype stage, probably ABS longer term but vac form process does not allow sufficient detail so aesthetic quality is less than desired with ABS.			Microcab vehicles will be used in shared economy, leased or in car club. Remanufacture will allow extended life so EOL of all parts and systems need to be considered and maximum value retained at each stage in vehicle's life.
Upholstered bed		Plastic components	Substitute plywood with an alternative material New particleboard with no added formaldehyde (NAF)	Improve the disassembly of the product (edge vs particleboard, upholster and fabrics);
Bookcase		Plastic components	Substitute plywood with an alternative material New particleboard with no added formaldehyde (NAF)	Improve the disassembly of the product (edge vs particleboard, upholster and fabrics);
OSB structural panel		The price is less than concurrent structural panel	Requirements: right value of vapour permeability, mechanical stability	Improve the disassembly of building walls and envelop : example use screws rather than nails or staple
plywood structural panel				Improve the disassembly of building walls and envelop : example use screws rather than nails or staple
Panel			Outdoor application, more durable than wood-based products	Due to much better durability than wooden counterparts, they are more suitable to enhance reuse strategies of circular economy. Opportunities for modularity and product as a service.
Pillars outdoor				
Non-woven	Re-granulation, web formation		Weight reduction	Recovery systems

Table 9 Details of the selection criteria per product

Figure 10 End of Life Baseline Scenario

Sector	End of Life – Baseline Data				Reference
	Reuse/Remanufacturing %	Recycling %	Incineration %	Landfill %	
Automotive	20	55	19	6	http://www.tms.org/pubs/journals/JOM/0308/Kanari-0308.html
Furniture	5	10	42	42	http://eeb.org/cutting-waste-could-boost-furniture-industry/
Building	10 (downcycle)	13	6	58	https://www.steelconstruction.info/Recycling_and_reuse

Table 10 End of Life Baseline Scenario

6.2.2 Data Collection

The data collection has been done using a specific template named “Products Card”, which includes all the crucial information related to the baseline KPIs and the value chain phases described in the previous sections. The products hereby reported represent the baseline for the 3 sectors of interest, Automotive, Furniture, and Building.

The collected Product Cards are available in Appendix II (confidential, only for members of the consortium). The following blank template is shown for the benefit of the reader to understand the structure of the information managed and as a reference for future implementation of baseline products that may be needed in the next phases of the EcoBulk project.

Product Name: Example Product Card				
Sector	<i>Automotive, Furniture, Building</i>			
Company	<i>Partner name</i>			
Component	<i>Component name</i>			
Application	<i>Ex. Outdoor, Internal finishing, etc...</i>			
Shape	<i>Ex. Complex 3D, panel, tube, etc...</i>			
Reference Materials	<i>Description of the current used materials:</i>			
	Material	Aesthetic/Colour	Designation	Weight (kg)
Alternative materials (Substitutes)	<i>Description of the alternative materials:</i>			
	Reference Material	Potential Material Substitute		
<i>Comments:</i>				

Product Name: Example Product Card		
Selection criteria (Circularity Challenges)	<i>Criteria for the selection of the component/product (Why you chose this component?):</i>	
	Currently difficult to be Recovered/Recycled	Y/N <i>If yes, please provide more info (ex. current recycling rate, etc...)</i>
	Difficulties in using/accepting recycled material for the use	Y/N <i>If yes, please provide more info (ex. aesthetic factors limiting use of recycled materials, Physical/Mechanical requirements etc...)</i>
	Critical application where composite materials can be a credible alternative	Y/N <i>If yes, please provide more info (ex. Physical/Mechanical requirements, life extension, etc..)</i>
	Where circular economy strategies and business models may be applied (e.g. recovery systems, product as a service, etc...)	Y/N <i>If yes, please provide more info</i>
Component Description	<i>Description (including pics) of:</i>	
	Design	<i>Description, picture</i>
	Geometry	<i>Description, picture</i>
	Assembly method	
	Manufacturing process	
	Finishing	
	<i>Comments:</i>	
Lifespan	<i>Current lifespan (yrs):</i> <i>Comments:</i>	
Supply chain	<i>Description of the current supply chain (actors, dimension, countries covered, waste streams)</i>	
Standards, Legislations	<i>Standards and legislations influencing the design, manufacturing and materials, marketing of the chosen product</i>	

Product Name: Example Product Card

Functional requirements	<i>Description of the KPI for the component (to act as baseline for new material/components testing/evaluation):</i>
	Physical/Mechanical Performances
	TOT Weight (kg)
	Manufacturing
	Aesthetic factors
	Target Cost
	Others
	<i>Comments:</i>

7 Environmental KPI elaboration

This section covers the summary of the calculated environmental KPI. The calculations are performed based on the Bill of Materials and processes reported in the baseline products card. The information has been inputted into the Granta Eco Audit model, which provides streamlined LCA results of the different products and components. The indicators of potential environmental impacts are:

- **Carbon footprint** or Global Warming potential: The CO₂-equivalent mass of greenhouse gases (kg CO₂e), in kg, produced and released into the atmosphere as a consequence of the production of 1 kg of the material. There are a variety of 'greenhouse gases' that contribute to global warming, including carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide. The 'potency' of these gases can vary significantly from a global warming perspective and therefore it is conventional to report these emissions in terms of an equivalent mass of carbon dioxide - kg CO₂e.
- **Embodied energy** or Cumulative Energy Demand: Gross Energy required to make 1 kg of the material from its ores or feedstocks, it is expressed in MJ (considering the Upper Heating Value of the fuels and energy used for the production)

The potential environmental impacts are calculated using Granta's Eco Audit module which consists of a streamlined LCA based on the Product Risk data module³¹. The scope of the evaluation is to elaborate an initial reference value for the further development expected in the next WPs activities.

First, the assembly information partially entered into the cards was considered. Next, each component in the assembly was mapped to a reference in the Granta eco data, based on the material description. For each material, a single main manufacturing process was also assigned to take into account the manufacturing environmental impact. In addition, the figure reported in the table below includes an average transport of 1000 km to take into account a "generic" logistic representative of an Europe distance range.

³¹ <https://www.grantadesign.com/products/ecoaudit/>

Sector	Application	Reference Product(s)	Life span [Years]	Weight [kg/unit]	Target cost [€/unit]	Embodied Energy [MJ]	Carbon Footprint [kgCO ₂ eq]
Automotive	Car interior	Fascia Central Console	5 - 7	0.22 – 0.26	5 - 7	24 - 26	1 - 2
		Safety belt brackets	10	0.15 – 0.20	2 - 4	6 - 8	0.5 – 0.7
		4WD control frame	10	0.09 – 0.1	2.70 - 3.00	11 - 12	0.6 – 0.65
		Centre Console Cowlings	5 - 10	0.1 - 1.82	40 - 60	16 - 17	0.65 – 0.75
Furniture	Home Furniture	Upholstered bed	10	80 - 100	1300 - 1800	1800 - 1900	80 - 90
		Bookcase	10	90 - 110	500 - 700	1300 - 1400	40 - 50
Building	Structural	OSB Structural Panel	100	30 - 35	16 - 18	300 - 400	12 - 14
		Plywood structural panel	100	80 - 90	60 - 70	1000 - 1010	30 - 40
	Outdoor (fencing, decking, etc...)	Solid Panel/Plank	10 - 15	2 - 3	4 - 6	20 - 30	0.95 – 1.05
		Post/Pillar	10 - 15	8 - 12	3 - 4	120 - 130	4 – 5
Various	Internal/soundproofing, thermal and structural insulation	Non-woven - Thermal and structural insulation(1m2)	10 - 15	35 - 45	150 - 170	3400 – 3600	120 – 130
		Non-woven - Floor carpets (1m2)	10 - 15	0.8 - 1	3 - 5	70 – 80	3 – 4

Table 11 Baseline environmental KPI

Figure 11 below shows a typical result from the EcoAudit Model (in this case the result of the Baseline product “Trim for central panel”). The general trends for these kinds of product is also shown in the image: material production can be considered the main contributor of impacts for the two indicators considered, followed by the manufacturing of the product itself (e.g injection moulding). The use phase has not been included in the analysis, since no product is an “energy using product”. But further investigation may be needed if any baseline may affect (positively or negatively) the use phase. Transport and end of life in the majority of cases do not represent a major concern. Nonetheless, it is important to consider with more in-depth analysis for the new solutions, since remanufacturing or recycling at the end of life would affect the environmental profile of new design considerably.

Figure 11 Example of Eco Audit output

8 Results and conclusion

The baseline investigated the main aspects related to sustainability and circular economy strategies of a variety of reference products and components. In Figure 12 and Figure 13, the graphs show how the baseline products are placed in a space of representing mass against Cost (expressed in EUR) and environmental impact (in this case Embodied Energy measured in MJ – considering that showing Carbon footprint would follow the same trend). We can see that the baseline product span from small product (low weight) and related impact–Automotive parts–to relatively high weight and impact products–Furniture.

Figure 12 Baseline: Cost versus Mass

In terms of environmental impacts, it can be seen that there is a more evident correlation with the mass, and this is mainly caused by the streamlined LCA that is based on the mass of the material used to carry out the analysis. Nonetheless, it is possible to see a correlation between polymer-based components (Fascia central console, 4WD control frame, floor carpet and insulation panel) laying almost on the same line. On almost parallel line below it is possible to notice the wood-based products, the upholstered bed is not perfectly in line because it is also using a mix of metals and polymers in various components e.g. legs and frame.

Figure 13 Baseline: Energy versus Mass

The previous two graphs are meant to show the wide range of applications that have been selected by the consortia, and will also inform the subsequent strategies to improve the circularity of the new solutions developed in the project. The next two graphs (Figure 14, Figure 15) are aiming at representing how the same baseline can be represented in terms of durability (life span expected for each product) and the cost intensity (as cost per kg) and energy intensity (as embodied energy per kg).

Figure 14 Baseline: Cost intensity versus Durability

When considering the cost or energy intensity, the first thing that stands out is the fact that the polymer-based products are now in the upper end of the graphs; this underlines how even if the automotive applications baseline are relatively small components, in large volumes this can produce a relatively important reduction in the overall impacts

Figure 15 Baseline: Energy intensity versus Durability

It is also interesting to note how the baseline products are generally positioned on a 10- 15 year scale, except for the construction panels that are intended to be used for the life span of the building, or in between major refurbishments. Also worth noting is how different energy/cost intensity product can be subject to different strategies for the general reduction of the environmental impacts, e.g.:

- The automotive baseline products are generally energy cost intensive, and at the same time difficult to be separated singularly before the end of life treatment. Therefore a possible strategy to reduce impacts and increase the circularity shall be based on the use of recycled/bio based materials.
- The furniture is already based on less energy-intensive materials, and the elongation of the parts life span, via refurbishment. Reuse may be one strategy to be pursued.
- For the building and furniture baseline products, based on wood materials, is important to consider that the preservation of the raw materials is a key parameter. The increase of recycled material content and the improvement of the current material use (e.g. reduce the formaldehyde free panel) are also critical parameters for the next activities foreseen in the project.

9 Appendix I: Social LCA in EcoBulk

9.1 (UNEP Guidelines methodology)

First, a literature review regarding the implementation of circular economy model in all the three industry sectors will be addressed, and/or any other studies related to this field which will be used as a data source. The methodology for the Social LCA will include:

- **Data collection:** perform interviews with manufacturers and any meaningful actors in EcoBulk; this is a pivotal step where reliability of data is fundamental.
- **Stakeholder Assessment:** identify groups of stakeholders (by *Wang* methodology) involved in the project and classify them (by *Ackerman and Eden* methodology) according to interest and influence in EcoBulk (e.g. local authorities, customers, R&D institutes, among others)
- **Indicators Selection:** define impact categories (e.g. Labour Practices, Human Rights, Society) and select subcategories and inventory indicators according to their relevance for the EcoBulk project (Employment, Innovation & Competitiveness, Community, etc.); measure the social impact of any activities through expert stakeholder feedback.
- **Social Life Cycle Assessment:** the final stage is to analyse the results and present the data presented graphically, deriving both final conclusions and mitigation strategies to deal with negative impact by internal and external surveys.

10 List of EcoBulk partners

Full Name	Short Name	Country
Akzo Nobel Industrial Coatings Ab	AKZO NOBEL	SE
Amiplas	AIMPLAS	ES
Asociacion Espanola De Normalizacion	UNE	ES
Bellver	BELLVER	ES
Centro Ricerche Fiat Scpa	CR FIAT SCPA	IT
Conenor Oy	Conenor	FI
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	CNR	IT
Cranfield University	CRANFIELD UNI	UK
Exergy Ltd	EXERGY	UK
Granta Design Ltd	GRANTA DESIGN	UK
Innovacio I Recerca Industrial I Sostenible SI	IRIS	ES
Institut Technologique Fcba (Foretcellulose Boisconstruction Ameublement)	FCBA	FR
Instituto Tecnologico Del Embalaje, Transporte Y Logistica	ITENE	ES
International Solid Waste Association	ISWA	AT
Kastamonu Entegre Agac Sanayi Ve Ticaret Anonim Sirketi	KEAS	TR
Kneia SI	KNEIA	ES
Maier Scoop	MAIER	ES
Microcab Industries Ltd	MICROCAB	UK
Moretti Compact	MORETTI	IT
Netcomposites Limited Coventive	NETCOMPOSITES Coventive	UK
Next Technology Tecnotessile Società Nazionale Di Ricerca R.L.	NTT	IT
Oakdene Hollins Limited	OAKDENE HOLLINS	UK
Servico Intermunicipalizado De Gestao De Residuos Do Grande Porto	LIPOR	PT
Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	NL
Technoplants Srl	Technoplants	IT
Tecnaro Gesellschaft zur industriellen Anwendung Nachwachsender Rohstoffe mbh	Tecnaro GmbH	DE
Tomra Sorting GmbH	TS	DE
Universitat Politecnica De Catalunya	UPC	ES
Vertech Group	VERTECH	FR

Table 12 List of Partners in EcoBulk Consortium

11 References

- Achterberg, E., Hinfelaar, J., & Bocken, N. (2016). Master circular business with the value hill. Amsterdam. Retrieved from <https://www.circle-economy.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/finance-white-paper-20160923.pdf>
- Allwood, J. M., Ashby, M. F., Gutowski, T. G., & Worrell, E. (2011). Material efficiency: A white paper. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 55(3), 362–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2010.11.002>
- Ashby, M. (2012). *Materials and the Environment: Eco-informed Material Choice: Second Edition*. *Materials and the Environment: Eco-informed Material Choice: Second Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2010-0-66554-0>
- Association of Plastics Manufacturers in Europe (1999), “Plastics: A Material of Choice for the Automotive Industry”, from <http://www.resol.com.br/textos/Plastics,%20a%20material%20of%20choice%20for%20the%20automotive%20industry.pdf>
- Beauson, J., Bech, J. I., & Brøndsted, P. (2014). Composite recycling: Characterizing end of life wind turbine blade material. In *Proceedings of 19th International Conference on Composite Materials* (p. 8).
- BS 8001:2017, Framework for implementing the principles of the circular economy in organizations- Guide
- BS 8887 2:2009 Design for manufacture, assembly, disassembly and end-of-life processing. Terms and definitions
- Buekens, A.; Zhou, X., “Recycling plastics from automotive shredder residues: A review”, *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manag.* (2014), 16, 398–414
- Circulate, “Developing a Circular Economy Approach in the Furniture Sector” (2015), from <http://circulatenews.org/2015/11/developing-a-circular-economy-approach-in-the-furniture-sector/>
- Composite Magazine, “Final Report on Composites Europe 2017”, from <http://www.compositimagazine.it/final-report-on-composites-europe-2017/>
- Composite World, “Composites recycling is gaining traction” (2017) , from <https://www.compositesworld.com/blog/post/composites-recycling-is-gaining-traction>
- Department for Business, Enterprise & Regulatory Reform, “Strategy for Sustainable Construction” (RSA, 2013) (BERR, 2008), from <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/+http://www.bis.gov.uk/files/file46535.pdf>
- European Environmental Bureau (EEB), “Report-on-the-Circular-Economy-in-the-Furniture-Sector” (2017), from www.eeb.org

European Parliament and Council, Directive 2008/98/EC on waste (Waste Framework Directive), from <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098>

European Parliament and Council. (2003). component and material coding standards for vehicles pursuant to Directive 2000/53/ EC.

European Parliament and Council. (2005). Directive 2005/64/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 October 2005 on the type-approval of motor vehicles with regard to their reusability, recyclability and recoverability and amending Council Directive 70/156/EEC. Retrieved February 7, 2018, from <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32005L0064>

Green Building Solutions, “Composites as High Performance Building Solutions”, from <https://greenbuildingsolutions.org/blog/composites-high-performance-building-solutions/> Adopted from The Ellen Macarthur Foundation and the UKs Waste Resources Action Programme

Hopewell, J., Dvorak, R., & Kosior, E. (2009). Plastics recycling: challenges and opportunities. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1526), 2115 LP-2126. Retrieved from <http://rstb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/364/1526/2115.abstract>

MarketsandMarkets™, “Composites Market by Fiber Type (Glass, Carbon), Resin Type (Thermoset, Thermoplastic), Manufacturing Process (Layup, Filament Winding, Pultrusion), Application (Transportation, Aerospace & Defense, Wind Energy), Region - Global Forecast to 2022” (2017), from <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/composite-market-200051282.html>

N. Kanari, J.-L. Pineau, and S. Shallari (JOM 2003), “End-of-Life Vehicle Recycling in the European Union”, *Minerals, Metals & Materials Society (TMS)*, from <http://www.tms.org/pubs/journals/JOM/0308/Kanari-0308.html>

NEN-ISO. (2008). *Plastics - Guidelines for the recovery and recycling of plastics waste (ISO 15270:2008, IDT)*. Retrieved February 9, 2018, from <https://connect.nen.nl/Standard/Detail/125821>

NEN-ISO. (2016). *ISO 11469: Generic identification and marking of plastic products*. Retrieved February 9, 2018, from <https://connect.nen.nl/Standard/Detail/226526>

PAS 100:2011 Specification for composted materials (BSI, January 2011), UKs Waste Resources Action Programme, from http://www.wrap.org.uk/sites/files/wrap/PAS%20100_2011.pdf

Perry, N., Bernard, A., Laroche, F., & Pompidou, S. (2012). Improving design for recycling – Application to composites. *CIRP Annals*, 61(1), 151–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CIRP.2012.03.081>

The Ellen Macarthur Foundation, “The Circular Economy Applied to the Automotive Industry” (2013), from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy/interactive-diagram/the-circular-economy-applied-to-the-automotive-industry>

The European Quality Association for Recycling e.V. (EQAR), “Recycling of building materials European market of quality-assured recycled building materials”, from <http://www.eqar.info/en/info-center/recycling-of-building-materials-for-nature-and-climate-protection.html>

Wienerberger, “Role of Construction Materials in the Circular Economy”, from <https://wienerberger.co.uk/about-us/role-of-construction-materials-in-the-circular-economy>

Wikipedia. (2018). Composite material. Retrieved February 9, 2018, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Composite_material